

Stiffness and Strength Properties of Woven Composites

T. Ishikawa, T. W. Chou

Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Delaware, Newark, Delaware 19711, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents four analytical models for the investigation of the stiffness and strength of woven fabric composites including hybrid cases. The "mosaic model" provides an approximate method for predicting the elastic moduli of fabric composites. The "fiber undulation model" takes into account fiber continuity and undulation and has been adopted for modelling the "knee behavior" of plain weave fabric composites. The "bridging model" is developed to simulate the load transfer among the interlaced regions in satin composites. The "modified bridging model" is proposed for extending the idea of the bridging action to the analysis of hybrid fabric composites. The theoretical predictions coincide extremely well with experimental measurements. The elastic stiffness and knee stress in satin composites are higher than those in plain weave composites due to the presence of the bridging regions in the weaving pattern.

INTRODUCTION

Woven fabrics are now considered to be a more important reinforcing material in the composite technology than a decade ago. The understanding of the reinforcing mechanics in fabric composites, however, has not been fully established yet. Although the structural efficiency of fabric composites is not as high as that of the unidirectional laminates, their versatile properties and low fabrication costs have made fabric composites attractive for structural applications [1,2].

This paper reports some recent findings in the study of undeveloped mechanics of fabric composites. A brief review of fabric categorization for both hybrid and non-hybrid cases will be given first. Four different models are then employed to approximate the elastic and strength behavior of fabric composites including hybrid ones. In the first model, known as the mosaic model, a fabric composite is idealized as an assemblage of asymmetrical cross-ply laminates [3,4]. Based upon the assumptions of the iso-stress and iso-strain, bounds of elastic moduli are derived and they provide an approximate method for predicting the elastic moduli and the results compare fairly well with experimental measurements [1].

In the second method, the mosaic model is modified to take into consideration the effect of fiber undulation and continuity on composite stiffness. A one-dimensional strip of the fabric composite forms the basis of the analysis and the classical laminated plate theory is applied to each infinitesimal piece of

the composite plate. The predictions of this model show good agreement with two-dimensional finite element results [5]. This approach, combined with some simple assumptions, has been extended to investigate the bi-linear or "knee" behavior of the stress-strain relations of plain weave composites. The results compare favorably with those obtained by other investigations [6].

The concept of the third model is developed based on the findings of load transfer in satin weave composites [7]. The region with straight threads surrounding an undulated interlaced region has higher local in-plane stiffness than the latter and acts as a load-transferring bridge. Numerical results of elastic moduli of graphite/epoxy exhibit a good agreement with experiments [1]. This model has also been extended to the analysis of the knee behavior in satin weave composites where the same assumptions about internal failure are employed. The predicted stress-strain curve shows an excellent correlation with the experimental curve [8] for glass/polyimide 8 harness satin composites.

The fourth model, which is referred to as the "modified bridging model," is specially derived for treating hybrid woven composites. The basic idea of the bridging action of the third model is preserved, although the geometry of this fourth model is much involved due to the complexity in the hybrid fabric structure. This model provides a significant improvement of the predictions of the simple bound results [4] and gives results very close to the experimental measurements of stiffness [1].

REVIEW OF FABRIC STRUCTURE AND MOSAIC MODEL

Most woven fabrics are formed by interlacing two sets of threads, the warp and the fill as shown in Fig. 1. The types of fabrics can be identified by the repeating patterns. Two geometrical parameters are defined first for identification; n_{fg} denotes that a warp thread is interlaced with every n_{fg} -th fill thread and n_{wg} denotes that a fill thread is interlaced with every n_{wg} -th warp thread. The attention of this paper is confined to the case of $n_{wg} = n_{fg} = n_g$. Fabrics with $n_g > 4$ and with isolated interlaced regions are known as satin weaves, and fabrics with $n_g = 2$ are known as plain weaves. Figure 1 depicts an 8 harness ($n_g = 8$) hybrid fabric. In the case of hybrid fabrics, parameters which define the material arrangements need to be defined. Figure 1 presents an example of $n_{fm} = 2$ and $n_{wm} = 3$; i.e., the pattern of arrangement of fiber types in the fill direction repeats for every two warp threads and that pattern in the warp direction repeats for every three fill threads where subscript m signifies a material parameter. Two implicit assumptions are adopted; no spacing between threads are allowed and hybrid fabrics consist of only two material types, denoted by α and β .

According to the previous investigation [4], some detailed categorization should be required for hybrids, such as homogeneous, heterogeneous and mixed interlacing types, which are related to a combination of integers n_g , n_{fm} and n_{wm} . However, the detail would be omitted here.

The hybrid fabrics are idealized as an assemblage of pieces of cross-ply laminates which consists of α and β materials because each rectangular area of Fig. 1 can be regarded as a piece of such a laminate.

Applying the classical laminate theory, the constitutive equations are

Fig.1 A hybrid woven Fabric with $n_g = 8$, $n_{fm} = 2$ and $n_{wm} = 3$.

$$N_i = A_{ij}^{\xi\eta} \epsilon_j^o + B_{ij}^{\xi\eta} \kappa_j, \quad M_i = B_{ij}^{\xi\eta} \epsilon_j^o + D_{ij}^{\xi\eta} \kappa_j \quad (1)$$

or in the inverted form

$$\epsilon_i^o = a_{ij}^{*\xi\eta} N_j + b_{ij}^{*\xi\eta} M_j, \quad \kappa_i = b_{ij}^{*\xi\eta} N_j + d_{ij}^{*\xi\eta} M_j \quad (2)$$

where N_i , M_i , ϵ_i^o and κ_i denote respectively membrane stress resultants, moments, strain and curvature at the geometrical mid-plane [9.10], and $i, j = 1, 2, 6$. Superscripts ξ and η represent respectively, the upper and lower layer material in the cross-ply. It is assumed here that the upper layer is occupied by the fill thread throughout the present analysis unless otherwise stated.

By adopting the assumption of iso-strain at the mid-plane, the upper bound of the elastic stiffness and the lower bound of the elastic compliance can be derived. Similarly, the assumption of iso-stress leads to the lower bound of the elastic stiffness and the upper bound of the elastic compliance.

FIBER UNDULATION MODEL

In this and the next section, non-hybrid fabrics consisting of α -material are discussed. Thus, the superscripts α as defined in Eqs.1 & 2 are omitted in equations in these two sections. Figure 2 depicts the geometry of the fiber undulation model. The shape of the fill thread can be expressed in the form of $h_1(x)$

$$h_1(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & (0 \leq x \leq a_0) \\ \left[1 + \sin\{(x-a/2)\pi/a_u\} \right] \cdot h_t/4 & (a_0 \leq x \leq a_2) \\ h_t/2 & (a_2 \leq x \leq n_g a/2) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The sectional shape of the warp thread is expressed by

$$h_2(x) = \begin{cases} h_t/2 & (0 \leq x \leq a_0) \\ [1 - \sin\{(x-a/2)\pi/a_u\}] h_t/4 & (a_0 \leq x \leq a/2) \\ - [1 + \sin\{(x-a/2)\pi/a_u\}] h_t/4 & (a/2 \leq x \leq a_2) \\ -h_t/2 & (a_2 \leq x \leq n_g a/2) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The fundamental assumption is that the classical laminate theory is applicable to each infinitesimal piece of the strip along the undulation direction. Under a uniformly applied N_1 , we define the averaged in-plane compliance by

$$\bar{a}_{ij}^{*U} = (1 - 2a_u/n_g) a_{ij}^{*} + 2/n_g a \cdot \int_{a_0}^{a_2} a_{ij}^{*}(x) dx \quad (5)$$

Note that a_{ij}^{*} denotes the in-plane compliance for the straight portion which is independent of x , and that superscript U signifies the solution of the fiber undulation model. By replacing a_{ij}^{*} in Eq.5 by d_{ij}^{*} , we have an expression of \bar{d}_{ij}^{*} . For the averaged coupling compliance, we have

$$\bar{b}_{ij}^{*U} = (1 - 2/n_g) b_{ij}^{*} + 2/n_g a \cdot \int_{a_0}^{a_2} b_{ij}^{*}(x) dx \quad (6)$$

The second term of Eq.6 vanishes because $b_{ij}^{*}(x)$ is an odd function of x with respect to $x=a/2$ due to the form of $h_1(x)$. It follows that \bar{b}_{ij}^{*U} in Eq.6 is

identical to the upper bound of compliance by the mosaic model. In other words, the fiber undulation has no effect on the coupling compliance.

The integrands $a_{ij}^*(x)$ and $d_{ij}^*(x)$ should be evaluated first. For this purpose, local plate stiffness coefficients are calculated such that

$$A_{ij}(x) = Q_{ij}^M (h_1(x) - h_2(x) + h - h_t/2) + Q_{ij}^F(\theta)h_t/2 + Q_{ij}^W(h_2(x) - h_1(x)) \quad (7)$$

where superscripts F, W, and M denote the fill and warp threads and matrix, respectively, and $0 \leq x < a/2$. Similar expressions can be written for $a/2 \leq x \leq na/2$. A consideration of off-axis local stiffness in the fill thread $Q_{ij}^F(\theta)$ should be required where θ is an off-axis angle and defined by

$$\theta(x) = \arctan(dh_1(x)/dx) \quad (8)$$

The following indirect procedure is adopted for determining $Q_{ij}^F(\theta)$ after Ref.5,

$$Q_{ij}^F(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} E_x^F(\theta)/D_v & E_{yx}^{Fv}(\theta)/D_v & 0 \\ E_{yx}^{Fv}(\theta)/D_v & E_y^F/D_v & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy}^F(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{where } i, j = 1, 2, 6 \text{ and } \quad (9)$$

$$D_v = 1 - \nu_{yx}^F(\theta)^2 E_y^F/E_x^F(\theta).$$

The elastic moduli in Eq. 9 are given by

$$\begin{aligned} E_x^F(\theta) &= 1/(\ell_\theta^4/E_x^F + (1/G_{xz}^F - 2\nu_{zx}^F/E_x^F)\ell_\theta^2 m_\theta^2 + m_\theta^4/E_x^F) \\ \nu_{yx}^F(\theta) &= \nu_{zx}^F \ell_\theta^2 + \nu_{yz}^F m_\theta^2, \quad G_{xy}^F(\theta) = G_{xy}^F \ell_\theta^2 + G_{yz}^F m_\theta^2 \\ E_y^F(\theta) &= E_y^F = E_z^F, \quad \text{where } \ell_\theta = \cos\theta, m_\theta = \sin\theta. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Note that transverse isotropy in the y-z plane of the fill thread is considered. Thus, one-dimensional average such as Eq.5 can be conceptually obtained. In the actual process, however, those integrations are conducted numerically. Finally, an inversion of a_{ij}^{*U} , E_{ij}^{*U} and d_{ij}^{*U} gives the elastic stiffness of this model, \bar{A}_{ij}^U , \bar{B}_{ij}^U and \bar{D}_{ij}^U . Numerical results for the in-plane stiffness will be shown later with the results of the bridging model as well.

This model is now extended to the analysis of the non-linear stress-strain behavior of plain weave composites. The reason why the application of the present model is limited to the plain weave composite will be stated later. Only the transverse internal failure which occurs in the warp threads under N_1 is considered here. Hence, the failure criterion based on the maximum strain ϵ_2^b is employed and we confine ourselves to the one-dimensional behavior. A bending-free case is considered first such as

$$\epsilon_1^o = a_{11}^* N_1 + b_{11} M_1^*, \quad \kappa_1 = b_{11}^* N_1 + d_{11}^* M_1 = 0 \quad (11)$$

Hence, we have the following modified in plane compliance a_{11}^* as

$$\epsilon_1^o = a_{11}^{**} N_1 \quad \text{where } a_{11}^{**} = a_{11}^* - b_{11}^{*2}/d_{11}^* \quad (12)$$

Since N_1 is uniform along the x-direction, $a_{11}^{**}(x)$ represents a strain distribution before the first transverse failure. The first failure occurs at the center of undulation where $x=a/2$ because the fiber undulation causes a local softening. Also, the strain along the z-direction at each section is uniformly equal to ϵ_1^o owing to the classical plate theory and the bending-free condition.

We consider the process that the highest strain in the region exceeds the specified strain ϵ_2^b first and, then, the failed area in the warp thread propagates as the load increases. It is assumed that the classical laminate theory is still valid in this failure process and that the effective elastic moduli of such a failed area are reduced to 1/100 of those of a sound area except for Q_{22}^W . By these assumptions, the progression of the failure can be traced for a small increment of the load. In the case where the bending by the coupling effect is allowed, some modifications in a formulation are required and the stress-strain curve can be again predicted [7]. However, numerical results are omitted here.

BRIDGING MODEL FOR SATIN WEAVE COMPOSITES

The success of the one-dimensional analysis leads to the idea of a bridging model for satin composites. Such a model is desirable in view of the fact that the interlaced regions in a satin are separated from each other. The geometry of the model is shown in Fig.3 where the shapes of the repeating regions are modified. This model is valid for only satin weaves where $n_g > 4$. The four regions labelled A, B, D and E consist of straight fill thread, and hence, can be regarded as pieces of cross-ply laminates of thickness h . Region C has an undulated fill and the continuity and undulation in the warp are ignored. The latter effect is expected to be small because an applied load is in the fill direction.

The in-plane stiffness in Region C where $n_g=2$ is found to be much lower than that of a cross-ply laminate where $n_g \rightarrow \infty$ in the previous section. Therefore, regions B and D carry higher loads than region C, if we assume that those three regions have the same averaged strain and curvature. Due to this assumption, we have

$$\bar{P}_{ij} = \{(\sqrt{n_g}-1)P_{ij} + P_{ij}^U\} / \sqrt{n_g} \quad (13)$$

$$\bar{B}_{ij} = (1 - 1/\sqrt{n_g}) B_{ij}$$

where P stands for A or D and the quantities without any superscript denote those of the cross-ply laminate. Also in Eq.13, a bar signifies the average in regions B, C and D and superscript U follows the previous convention in Eq.5. It is assumed that the total in-plane force carried by these three regions is equal to that by region A or E. Then the averaged compliance can be written as

$$\bar{P}_{ij}^* S = 2/\sqrt{n_g} \cdot \bar{P}_{ij}^* + (1-2/\sqrt{n_g}) P_{ij}^* \quad (14)$$

where p stands for a, b or d and superscript S indicates the properties of the entire satin plate. The compliance \bar{p}_{ij} in Eq.14 is obtained by inversion of \bar{A}_{ij} , etc. in Eq. 13. The results of stiffness of this model \bar{A}_{ij}^S , etc., are obtained by inverting \bar{p}_{ij}^S in Eq.14.

Numerical results for the relationships between the non-dimensional in-plane stiffness with respect to A_{11} and $1/n_g$ is indicated in Fig.4. The thread V_f is assumed to be 65% and 60% for the bridging and fiber undulation models, respectively. The properties of UD laminae are listed in Table 1 for graphite/epoxy as well as other systems appearing later. The results by the fiber undulation model coincide well with the corresponding finite element results [5]. The curve by the bridging model shows an excellent agreement with an experimental point by Ref.1. It should be noted here that experiments for the cross-ply laminate are in good agreement with the prediction by the laminate theory.

Fig.3 Bridging model (a) shape of a repeating unit of 8 harness satin (b) modified square shape (c) basic idealization

Fig.4 \bar{A}_{11}/A_{11} vs. $1/n_g$ for graphite/epoxy fabric. —:bound theory, ---:fiber undulation model, - - -:bridging model, \blacktriangle and \circ :FEM results for respective models, and \bullet : experimental results for 8 harness satin.

The reason why the fiber undulation model is effective for plain weave composites whereas the bridging model is valid for satin weave composites is stated below. There are no straight thread regions surrounding an interlaced region and the one-dimensional distribution of in-plane stiffness is identical in each thread in a plain weave composite. It can be expected, therefore, that no bridging effect occurs in the plain weave composite and that each thread carries the same in-plane force. Hence, the one-dimensional and bridging approaches are suitable for the plain and satin weave composites, respectively.

The concept of the successive failure employed previously can be extended to the bridging model. For the bending-free case, we have

$$\bar{A}_{11}^* = 1/\sqrt{n_g} \cdot \bar{A}_{11}^{*U} + (1-1/\sqrt{n_g}) A_{11}^* \quad (15)$$

where $A_{11}^* = 1/a_{11}^{**}$. Here, a_{11}^{**} follows the definition in Eq.12. Due to the uniformity of N_1 we obtain

$$a_{11}^{**S} = 2/\sqrt{n_g} \cdot a_{11}^{**} + (1-2/\sqrt{n_g}) a_{11}^{**} \quad (16)$$

$$\bar{A}_{11}^{*S} = 1/a_{11}^{**S} \quad \text{where} \quad \bar{a}_{11}^{**} = 1/\bar{A}_{11}^*$$

The rest of the procedure is quite similar to the previous section. Figure 5 compares numerical and experimental results for stress-strain curves of 8 harness satin and plain weave plates of glass/polyimide system whose material properties are indicated in Table 1. Due to the configuration of the test pieces, the bending-free condition is selected for comparison. A very good correlation between theory and experiments is obtained. If we define a knee point by a deviation of 0.01% in strain from the linear state, we observe that knee stress in the 8 harness satin is higher than that of the plain weave composites.

Fig.5 Stress-strain curves for a glass/PI
 —:bridging result for 8 satin,
 ---:fiber undulation for plain (both no κ)
 -·-·:experimental curve, and ●:knee point.

MODIFIED BRIDGING MODEL FOR HYBRID SATIN COMPOSITES

The idea of the bridging action developed in the last section is now applied to the hybrid satin weave composites. In contrast to the development of the general formulae for the bound theory (Sec.2), the pattern of fabric interlacing needs to be specified for the present model. In the following discussion, three cases of 8 harness satin of homogeneous interlacing are chosen; they are (3,1;3,1), (1,1;1,1) and (1,3;1,3). Here, the four integers in the parentheses correspond to n_{fm}^α , n_{fm}^β , n_{wm}^α and n_{wm}^β , respectively[4]. The geometry of the modified bridging model for (3,1;3,1)-case is shown in Fig.6. This model corresponds to the minimum repeating unit in the rectangle shape. The fiber undulation and continuity are taken into account. The sinusoidal shape of the fill is assumed to be the same as that defined by Eqs.3 & 4. However, the effect of the thread width ratio comes into play in the hybrids. The local stiffness is obtained for α -warp portion as

$$A_{ij}^{\xi\alpha}(x) = Q_{ij}^M \{h - h_c/2 + h_1^\alpha(x) - h_2^\alpha(x)\} + Q_{ij}^{F\xi}(\theta) h_c/2 + Q_{ij}^{W\alpha} \{h_2^\alpha(x) - h_1^\alpha(x)\} \quad (17)$$

where ξ stands for a material of the fill, α or β . The rest of the local stiffness coefficients is calculated in a similar manner. It is convenient here to reduce the averaging unit length to a half pitch of the undulation such as

$$\bar{a}_{ij}^{*U\xi\alpha} = 2/a \cdot \int_0^{a/2} a_{ij}^{*\xi\alpha}(x) dx = (1 - a_u/a) a_{ij}^{*\xi\alpha} + 2/a \cdot \int_{a_0}^{a_1} a_{ij}^{*\xi\alpha}(x) dx \quad (18)$$

where the conventions in superscripts of the preceding sections are followed.

Now consider region R_2 in Fig.6 as an example. Region R_2 can be divided into sub-regions R_2^1 to R_2^4 . The properties of regions R_2^1 and R_2^2 are the same and their compliance is given

$$p_{ij}^*(R_2^1) = (3p_{ij}^{*\alpha\alpha} + rp_{ij}^{*\alpha\beta}) / (3+r) \quad (19)$$

where p stands for a, b or d . Similarly, for region R_2^4 ,

$$p_{ij}^*(R_2^4) = (3p_{ij}^{*\beta\alpha} + rp_{ij}^{*\beta\beta}) / (3+r) \quad (20)$$

By considering a cancellation of the b_{ij}^* in the undulation, we have

$$\bar{b}_{ij}^*U(R_2^3) = (\bar{b}_{ij}^*U\alpha\alpha - r\bar{b}_{ij}^*U\alpha\beta) / (3+r) \quad (21)$$

The \bar{a}_{ij}^* and \bar{d}_{ij}^* here are given by

$$q_{ij}^*U(R_2^3) = (3q_{ij}^*U\alpha\alpha - q_{ij}^*U\alpha\beta) / (3+r) \quad (22)$$

where q represents a or d . The averaged stiffness for each sub-region is obtained by inversion. Then, A_{ij} in region R_2^3 can be expressed as $\bar{A}_{ij}^U(R_2^3)$. By using the previous assumption that all strains are the same in the bridging regions, the averaged stiffness in the entire region R_2 can be obtained as

$$\bar{P}_{ij}^U(R_2) = \{2\bar{P}_{ij}^U(R_2^1) + \bar{P}_{ij}^U(R_2^3) + r\bar{P}_{ij}^U(R_2^4)\} / (3+r) \quad (23)$$

where P again denotes A, B or D .

Similar procedures are taken for the other regions.

Finally, by assuming uniformity of the in-plane force, the compliance of the entire model of Fig. 6 is given by

$$p_{ij}^{*HS} = \{3p_{ij}^*(R_1) + (3+r)\bar{p}_{ij}^*(R_2)/2 + (1+r)\bar{p}_{ij}^*(R_3)/2 + (1+r)\bar{p}_{ij}^*(R_5)\} / \{2(3+r)\} \quad (24)$$

Here, superscript HS signifies hybrid satin weaves. It should be noted that the compliance of region R_1 is the same as that of region R_4 . The inversion of, e.g., \bar{a}_{ij}^{*HS} etc., gives results for the stiffness \bar{A}_{ij}^{*HS} . By interchanging the α and β materials, results for the (1,3;1,3) case can be readily obtained. However, different formulations are required for the (1,1;1,1) case and they are omitted here.

Numerical results of the present theory are indicated in Fig.7 based upon the basic material properties of graphite and Kevlar/epoxy of $V_f=65\%$ of Table 1 as well as the results of the bound theory. The experimental results of hybrid fabric composites [1] with the same fabric parameters as the theory compares very favorably with the modified bridging

Fig.6 Modified Bridging model

Fig.7 \bar{A}_{11}/h vs. relative V_f . MB: Modified bridging model, ● and ▲: experimental results [1] for fabric & laminate, respectively, —, —; bound theory.

Table 1 Material properties of UD lamina

Material	Graphite/Epoxy [12]	
V_f^*	65%	60%
E_L	132	113
E_T	9.31	8.82
G_{LT}	4.61	4.46
ν_{TL}	0.28	0.3
t (mm)	0.4	0.4
Material	Kev. [13]/Ep. Glass/PI \$ [11]	
V_f^*	65%	50%
E_L	85.3	41.2
E_T	5.50	15.7
G_{LT}	2.54	5.59
ν_{TL}	0.4	0.3
ϵ_2^b	#	0.45%
t (mm)	0.4	0.244

*: V_f in threads, \$: polyimide
: no strength calculation
Unit: GP_a for moduli

results which fall between the bound curves. As expected, the upper bound prediction is very close to the experimental results of interlaminated hybrids. The solution of the limiting case where $r = 1$ and α and β are of the same material provides a comparison of the present model for the non-hybrid fabric with the previous bridging model. The comparison gives less than 1.1% discrepancy in A_{11} between these two models. It should be mentioned that besides Fig. 6 there exists other possible choices of repeating units as well as sub-region divisions although they lead to quite similar results.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The mosaic model provides rough but simple predictions of the elastic moduli of fabric composites including hybrid cases. This model also facilitates the categorization of hybrid fabrics.
2. The fiber undulation model based upon a one-dimensional strip demonstrates a softening effect in the in-plane stiffness as compared to cross-ply laminates. This approach is suitable particularly for plain weave composites and the theory compares very favorably with finite element results. This model has been applied to examine the knee behavior of plain weave composites.
3. The bridging model is developed to investigate the stiffness and strength of non-hybrid satin weave composites. The basic concept is to idealize a repeating region of a satin in which the interlaced region is separated from one another. The regions with straight threads surrounding an interlaced region have higher in-plane stiffness and play the role of load-transferring bridges. The theoretical results of stiffness demonstrate a good agreement with experimental data. This approach is also extended to the study of a nonlinear behavior in satin composites. A theoretical prediction for an 8 harness satin of glass/polyimide compares excellently well with the experimental curve. The elastic stiffness and knee stress in satin composites are higher than those in plain weave composites due to the presence of the bridging regions.
4. The concept of the bridging model has been applied to an analysis of elastic stiffness of hybrid fabric composites. Numerical results of this modified bridging model fall in between the predictions of the simple bounds and show a remarkable agreement with experimental results.

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